

BEST-CSP benchmark study of polymorphs I and II of sulfamerazine and the perils of polytype polymorphs

Contribution by the Červinka group

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We used the quasi-harmonic approximation (QHA)¹ to model structural and thermodynamic properties of selected sulfamerazine polymorphs. Within QHA, unit-cell geometries are repeatedly optimized at various constrained volumes, resulting in sampling the dependence of the static electronic energy of the crystal on its volume. Around the minimum of this energy – volume dependence, harmonic phonon calculations are performed with the finite-displacement method for eight crystal volumes, sampling the anharmonic dependence of phonon frequencies on crystal volume. Phonon calculations were performed for supercells spanning at least 10 Å in each direction, allowing for a reasonable treatment of the impact of phonon dispersion on thermodynamic properties of the crystal.¹ To save computational resources, the composite formulation of QHA,² combining full (volume-dependent) QHA at a low QM level of theory with a single-volume harmonic calculation with a more sophisticated method to correct the output of the cheaper method, was followed. Semi-empirical third-order density-functional tight binding DFTB3 theory³ within periodic boundary conditions was used along the D4 dispersion correction⁴ and the 3ob parametrization,⁵ implemented in the DFTB+ code, version 24.1,⁶ as the low-level QM method with the composite QHA. The high-level of theory within our composite QHA was selected from the density-functional theory framework. Periodic PBE-D4 model^{4,7} was used along with the PAW formalism⁸ (hard PAW potentials and 1000 eV plane-wave kinetic-energy cut-off), implemented in VASP, version 6.4.2.⁹⁻¹¹ See our previous publication for more details on the composite QHA computational setup.² All underlying electronic-structure calculations were performed using a 3×2×1 *k*-point mesh to sample the respective *k*-space for unit-cell optimizations, whereas only the electronic Γ -point was sampled for the supercells upon phonon modeling.

We focused only on sulfamerazine forms I and II. Complete QHA results for form I are presented and discussed in this work. Comparing the calculated isobaric heat capacities for the form I with reference experimental values reveals a very good agreement of our composite QHA model, yielding slightly underestimated results, but in general differing by only 2–3% over a broad temperature interval. That can be considered as a very good computational accuracy considering the typical heat capacity outcomes of the QHA model relying on PBE-D

theories.^{1,2,12,13} Interestingly, the composite QHA model predicts a relatively low (1% on the relative scale) difference between the quasi-harmonic isobaric and harmonic isochoric heat capacity of the form I, which can be understood as an imprint of a lesser thermal expansion of the crystal at near-ambient conditions. Within the harmonic model only, both DFTB and PBE models agree closely on the C_V of the form I at ambient conditions. However, the quasi-harmonic model relying solely on the DFTB theory overestimates C_p (by 2–5%), and this computational artifact is even more amplified at elevated temperatures. Performing the composite QHA, correcting the DFTB outputs to match the PBE outcome at a reference volume then improves the overall C_p appreciably. All sets of calculated heat capacities for the SMZ form I are listed in Table S1.

Table S1

Form I heat capacities (in J/mol/K) as calculated by the Cervinka group

T [K]	Expt.	DFTB HA	DFTB	PBE HA	Composite QHA	Percentage
form I	C_p	only	QHA	only	PBE:DFTB	error of the
		C_V	C_p	C_V	C_p	PBE:DFTB
						data set
240	245.8	239.9	257.0	238.7	239.9	-2.4%
245	250.1	244.0	261.4	242.9	244.1	-2.4%
250	254.4	248.1	265.8	247.0	248.4	-2.4%
255	258.6	252.1	270.2	251.2	252.6	-2.3%
260	262.6	256.1	274.6	255.3	256.8	-2.2%
265	267.4	260.1	278.9	259.4	261.0	-2.4%
270	271.5	264.1	283.2	263.5	265.3	-2.3%
275	275.7	268.1	287.5	267.5	269.4	-2.3%
280	280.0	272.0	291.7	271.6	273.6	-2.3%
285	284.3	275.9	296.0	275.6	277.8	-2.3%
290	288.5	279.8	300.2	279.7	281.9	-2.3%
295	292.8	283.7	304.4	283.7	286.1	-2.3%
300	297.1	287.5	308.5	287.6	290.2	-2.3%
305	301.3	291.3	312.7	291.6	294.3	-2.3%
310	305.6	295.1	316.9	295.5	298.3	-2.4%
315	309.9	298.9	321.1	299.4	302.4	-2.4%
320	314.2	302.6	325.3	303.3	306.4	-2.5%
325	318.5	306.4	329.6	307.2	310.4	-2.5%
330	322.7	310.1	333.8	311.0	314.3	-2.6%
335	326.9	313.7	338.2	314.8	318.2	-2.7%
340	331.1	317.3	342.5	318.6	322.0	-2.7%
345	335.4	321.0	347.0	322.4	325.9	-2.8%
350	339.6	324.5	351.4	326.1	329.6	-2.9%

Current composite QHA model underestimates the equilibrium unit-cell volume of SMZ form I at finite temperatures by 5.6% which is not particularly good result when compared to a typical performance of DFT-D powered QHA models of molecular crystals.^{1,2,12,13} However, the current model consistently maintains that percentage volume error over a broad temperature interval, spanning from 30 K to 200 K as listed in Table S2. That indicates that the thermal expansion of this crystal structure is captured very well. SMZ form I expands its volume by 2.2% upon heating from 30 K to 200 K as observed experimentally, whereas our model states this value at 2.3%. Due to the orientation of the hydrogen bonding (N–H...N and N–H...O bonds) predominantly in direction of the lattice vector a , impeding thus the expansion of the material in this direction, most of this thermal expansion manifests in directions of the lattice vectors b and c , where weaker dispersion interaction govern the crystal cohesion. On the other hand, calculated equilibrium lengths of the b and c lattice vectors are the dominant error sources for the overall overestimation of the bulk crystal density at finite temperatures. Calculated linear expansion in the directions of the a , b and c lattice vectors reach 0.0%, 1.3%, and 1.0%, respectively. Both theory and experiment agree on this behavior closely, confirming the previously observed capability of our QHA models to capture the anisotropy of thermal expansion due to the directionality of site-specific cohesive interactions in the crystal structure.¹⁴ Such results justify the functionality of the composite QHA model also for the treatment of anisotropic thermal expansion.

Table S2

Thermal expansion of SMZ form I documented with values of the unit-cell volume (V , in Å³) its percentage error δ_V and lattice parameters (a , b , c , all in Å) as calculated by the Cervinka g-roup, compared with values interpolated from raw experimental data assembled in this work.

T	Experiment				Composite QHA PBE:DFTB				
	a	b	c	V	a	b	c	V	δ_V
30	14.535	8.226	22.042	2635.2	14.658	7.952	21.347	2488.2	-5.6%
40	14.539	8.228	22.057	2638.3	14.658	7.955	21.354	2490.0	-5.6%
60	14.540	8.229	22.087	2642.9	14.657	7.964	21.372	2494.7	-5.6%
80	14.542	8.232	22.120	2648.3	14.656	7.975	21.395	2500.7	-5.6%
100	14.549	8.237	22.158	2655.5	14.654	7.987	21.421	2507.1	-5.6%
120	14.559	8.243	22.199	2663.9	14.653	8.000	21.448	2514.2	-5.6%
140	14.569	8.247	22.239	2672.2	14.651	8.014	21.476	2521.6	-5.6%
160	14.576	8.251	22.276	2679.3	14.652	8.027	21.505	2529.2	-5.6%
180	14.582	8.256	22.311	2685.7	14.650	8.041	21.535	2536.8	-5.5%
200	14.592	8.261	22.352	2694.3	14.652	8.054	21.565	2544.8	-5.5%
220	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	14.652	8.068	21.595	2552.8	n/a
240	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	14.653	8.081	21.626	2560.8	n/a
260	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	14.655	8.094	21.657	2568.9	n/a
280	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	14.658	8.107	21.687	2577.1	n/a

300	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	14.660	8.120	21.718	2585.3	n/a
320	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	14.664	8.132	21.749	2593.5	n/a
340	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	14.668	8.144	21.780	2601.8	n/a
Δ^a	0.057	0.035	0.310	59.1	-0.006	0.102	0.218	56.6	-4.2%

^a Quantity Δ stands for the absolute differences between the form I structures at 200 K and 30 K.

Despite our efforts to optimize the unit-cell geometry of the form II to relatively tight convergence criteria with both DFTB3-D4/3ob and PBE-D4/PAW models, subsequent phonon calculations always yielded multiple imaginary phonon modes which restrained us from calculations of thermodynamic properties for that polymorph.

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Acknowledgement

Computational resources were provided by the e-INFRA CZ project (ID:90254), supported by the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic. C. Č. and R. G. acknowledge the support by the project "The Energy Conversion and Storage", funded as project No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004617 by Programme Johannes Amos Comenius, call Excellent Research.